

Tuesday, November 25, 2025 at 12:47:13 PM Eastern Standard Time

Subject: ICO Case Reference: IC-384513-B5V6

Date: Wednesday, October 29, 2025 at 8:15:20 AM Eastern Daylight Saving Time

From: icocasework

To: Yiftach Fehige

29 October 2025

Case Reference: IC-384513-B5V6

Dear Yiftach Fehige

We last corresponded with you about your FOIA complaint about Kings College London in August. I apologise for the delay in allocating your case but it has now been allocated to me. I've written to Kings College and am expecting to receive its submission after the middle of November. Once I've received the submission, and when I have the opportunity to do so, I'll progress your case further.

I hope this is helpful in the meantime.

Yours sincerely

Senior Case Officer
Information Commissioner's Office

Information Commissioner's Office, Wycliffe House, Water Lane, Wilmslow, Cheshire SK9 5AF

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